

NUMERICAL STUDY OF LAY-UP AND BONDING METHOD OPTIMIZATION UNDER BENDING-TORSION LOAD CONDITION FOR LARGE SCALE COMPOSITE WIND-TURBINE BLADE

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ABSTRACT

A wind power plant is a device that converts the kinetic energy of the wind into mechanical energy, which is then turned into electricity. The wind power plant therefore uses wind speed to produce renewable energy with very low greenhouse gas emissions or waste. Onshore wind power plants are installed on land, unlike offshore plants, which are in the sea. Offshore wind-turbines need good oxidation resistance and mechanical reliability. Composites materials are the best considerations to resist random wind force for long time operation. A numerical simulation was implemented to predict the stress distribution over a wind-blade. The required material and bonding properties that are needed for large-scale composite blades are studied using Finite Element Analysis by Abaqus software. Composite material has an orthotropic nature which leads to structural damage variation based on ply orientation and stack thickness. The composite material structure that can withstand the stress-strain field obtained and which can optimize the fabrication technologies of critical zones depending upon the stack thickness, ply orientation and bonding techniques were discussed. The root section and trailing edge were found to be critical zones in the wind turbine blade. The root section deformation can be reduced by adjusting the thickness of the structure. On the other hand, the trailing-edge deformation is influenced by bonding method. Moreover, an improvement of existing joining technology is imperative to reduce the maximum stress concentration at these edges. The results show that the found optimized ply orientation and adequate joining technology for carbon and glass-fibre composites to lower the failure.

1 INTRODUCTION

The recent fast growth in wind energy production motivates wind power industries to design large scale wind-turbines, in order to reduce the cost of energy. According to the world energy association, the modern wind turbines are 100 times bigger than the traditional ones. As the result, wind energy industries are motivated to develop advanced materials to withstand high wind forces reacting on rotor blades. Composite materials with their high strength-to-weight characteristics and associated stiffness are finding wide use in wind turbine component production. The up-scaling requires design optimizations for an increase in strength, as well as a reduction in weight and cost of energy. Composite material properties are optimized according to load considerations. The orthotropic parameters of composite materials vary depending on the fiber stiffening directions. In light of this, the fiber direction should be selected to enhance the strength in the directions which need a high stiffness.

Bending and torsion loads are sustained by optimal ply orientation and layup arrangement. The efficient transfer of load through composite assembly requires bonded or fastened joints. Often, blade sub-components are glued together. The main scope of manufacturers is to reduce the blade maintenance cost for offshore wind turbine blades because maintenance expenses increase the total cost of energy in offshore installations compared to their onshore counterparts [13]. Bonding alone makes the maintenance and repair workers to detach and lower the blade to the ground for repairs. Bonding materials become brittle after they are cured, with low brittle strength values. They lose bonding strength (stickiness) through micro-cracks. The study of bonding material is imperative to develop additional strength in adhesive bonding zones.

Composite material optimization with advanced bonding techniques is essential for large scale wind turbine blade structure. Cox et al. [5] studied structural design for large-scale wind turbine blades. Their research gathered the material types for each blade component and the load acting under extreme condition. In addition, it explains the buckling phenomena and ply drop avoidance methods for numerical simulation. Wind turbine blade design and numerical simulation conditions are studied in different projects [1, 7, 12]. Zhimin Li et al. [19] investigated the effect of layup on wind turbine blade properties. They calculate to study the strength and mass distribution along the blade span. Zhang et al. [21] investigated the effect of thickness and layup on composite materials used in wind turbine blades. This method helps to design a blade model with shell elements and compares experimental results with numerical ones to reduce the weight and gravitational force of wind turbine blades. Ashwill et al. [7] in Sandia laboratory studied the coupling of bending and torsion forces acting on blade made of composites. The blade material undergoes the coupling of these forces and must be capable of withstanding them. Ganz et al. [18] investigated the advantage of composite materials over isotropic materials. They also studied failure measurement based on Tsai-Wu values. Stickler et al. [15] studied the numerical analysis of bonding of composite structures and the effective way to bond composite structures. Tong et al [10] provided a good view of stitching of composite materials to increase the strength of composite bonds. Some other researches gave knowledge of damage prevails in composite adhesive bonding [8, 9, 17, 22]. Stitching combined with bonding would reinforce the adhesive material strength based on stitching fiber and sewing pitch. This will hold the blade bonding area in place even after crack initiation [14], so the repair technicians do not need to disassemble the blade from the hub.

The current work presents a wind turbine blade made of composite material with unidirectional and woven fabric combinations. The simulation is done in static 3-point bending and end point twist load. The damage in each ply is observed visually by failure criteria factors called Tsai-Wu criterion. Adhesive bonding is included in this numerical study to clearly identify and specify bonding requirements. Observation of failure factor in the bonding zones with the composite stitching technology was included in the numerical simulation to bring the analysis process close to real manufacturing procedures.

2 NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

2.1 Blade design

For large scale wind turbine configurations, high areas of rotation induce extreme mass flow through the blade, so the blade should withstand the high mass flow rate and the relative forces caused by the same. It is therefore compulsory to proceed through numerical study for material development in fabrication of blades whilst concentrating on large blade configuration. The primary design of the blade was configured by Python codes to achieve the accurate dimensions, the airfoil modelling and the section interact splines between the planes. Each part can be programmed independently and they get assembled in Abaqus. The blade is designed by 2D shell elements. The blade root is considered as circular section and towards tip the blade gets the form of airfoil. The airfoil profile NACA 63XXX series was used to design the blade. In the present model, the blade is designed by skin and spars with box beam. Real case blades contain ribs and other additional structures inside the skin to provide high strength, but consideration of the whole structure will complicate in the analysis. So, we selected only the skin and spars to study the material properties and the method for improving rigidity. The blade

length is 70m and the chord length at the root is equal to 3m. The chord length at the tip is considered as 1.5m. The blade has a twist throughout the span. This twist is assumed 15° from root to tip. In other words, the root plane and tip plane are orientated by 15° from one to the other. The blade contains 2 spars along the span wise orientation of the rotor to withstand the bending forces and the chord wise inertial forces. The shear web shapes are designed to withstand the shear forces acting on the large scale assembly. They are box beam sections fixed with skin. The following Fig.2 shows the designed aerodynamic configurations and the final model of the blade in the Abaqus user interface.

Figure 1: Loads and boundary conditions of blade

In this analysis, unidirectional tapes and woven fabrics which are oriented in different angles were used. Woven fabrics are normally used to give high tensile force and shear resistance. In this study, the blade is simulated in linear static condition under bending and torsion coupling loads see Equation (3) [2]. G is a stiffness matrix which is function of flap-wise displacement θ , M_b and M_t are the bending moment and twisting moment, EI , GJ are bending and torsion variables based on material and dimensions. Bending loads are applied at 3 points a, b, c which are located at 2 m, 20 m and 45 m consequently from the blade tip (see Fig.1).

$$dT = \frac{1}{2} \rho V o^2 4Fa(1 - a)2\pi r dr \quad \text{-----} \quad (1)$$

$$dQ = \frac{1}{2} \rho V o^2 4F(1 - a)a' \frac{\omega r}{V_o} r 2\pi r dr \quad \text{-----} \quad (2)$$

Calculations were carried out at a wind speed of 15m/s by blade element theory [3] that provides a 150 KN bending force distributed in 3-points (40 KN at point a, 50 KN at point b, 60 KN at Point c) and 300 KN-m twisting moment at shear center in blade tip chord section (from Equation (1)). In here, dT and dQ represent the thrust and torque equations of a finite number of blade elements.

$$\begin{bmatrix} EI & -g \\ g & GJ \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial x} \begin{bmatrix} M_b \\ M_t \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{-----} \quad (3)$$

Figure 2: Blade numerical model constructed by various several planes to maintain the twist angle.

2.2 COMPOSITE MATERIAL DESCRIPTION

Large number of blade materials was used successfully for wind turbine blades. Nowadays, blades designer are primarily working with fiber-glass composites. The increase in rotor size and the various designs constraint and motivate the designers to work with other materials or to use the current material with innovative ways. The carbon/epoxy (CFRP) composite and glass/vinyl-ester (GFRP) composites are considered in this paper [4]. The majority of blades are modelled by using glass fiber composite. Adding carbon fibers in given percentage will increase the stiffness and reduce the weight of the structure [5].

Figure 3: Blade model, after section division

The skin and spars are the two main components used in this study. Other substructures are neglected for simplification. The blade contains 2 spars placed throughout the lengthwise direction of blade. The spar web is made of sandwich material which contains foam as a core. The foam material

properties are gathered from TYCOR W-series type foams (Table. 1). The spar flange is designed by unidirectional composite tapes to provide high bending stiffness. The skin of the sandwich structure can be designed with glass fiber composite or carbon composites arranged in different angles to provide the damage resistance. Glass Woven fabrics or carbon woven materials are also studied instead of unidirectional tapes. For industrial applications, the designer selects weaved composites rather than unidirectional composites because of their strength dispersion in all directions. Unidirectional composites are better if the force is applied along the longitudinal direction of the fiber. The transverse modulus of the unidirectional composites is too small compared to the longitudinal modulus, but wind turbine undergoes random wind loads. Hence, blade should be made of the material which has the rigidity along all directions. The leading edge section is considered to have foam inside composite layups to resist bending load reacting in direct contact with the blade while the rotor is in the electric energy production. Blade is modelled with different sections to give different composite layup properties in different sections (see the Fig. 3). This helps to reduce the weight and make the analysis as true-to-life as possible [21]. To define the materials in different sections of the rotor blade, the blade design is divided according to necessary dimensions. This segmentation also allows defining different materials thickness and orientations. Difference in thicknesses in various sections causes the ply drop effects. To avoid the ply drop effect during the calculation, we consider several 0° plies in-between the other plies [5]. The section thickness is varied gradually for the consecutive adjacent section; this keeps away the sudden ply drop effect between the sections. In this simulation, we are going to see the optimal material orientation and fiber directions. The material mechanical properties are shown in the Table 1. Each ply is designed with 1.25mm thickness.

Table 1: Material properties

Materials	E_1	E_2	ν_{12}	G_{12}	G_{23}
Woven fabrics - Glass	23.37 GPa	23.50 GPa	0.28	5.22 GPa	4.74 GPa
Woven fabrics - Carbon	63 GPa	62.73 GPa	0.05	4.37 GPa	2.91 GPa
Unidirectional - Glass	47.10 GPa	13.098 GPa	0.28	4.749 GPa	3.134 GPa
Unidirectional - Carbon	103.3 GPa	9 GPa	0.05	5.32 GPa	3.51 GPa
Material	Young's modulus	density			
Adhesive material	275 MPa	1420 Kg/m ³			
Foam	220 MPa	153 Kg/m ³			

In addition, blade components are bonded by adhesive materials. The upper and lower sections of blades are bonded with high strength adhesive material (Fig. 6). This adhesive layer is included in this simulation to identify whether the adhesive material alone can resist the high coupling force or not. Blade ply orientation and thickness would be optimized under bending and torsion combined loading and the failure would be identified by Tsai-Wu failure criteria value. This optimized structure helps to study precisely stress distribution over the length of the blade and the adhesive material properties are identified. Macroplast UK1340 type adhesive is used for bonding material (Table. 1).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Study of material and ply orientation

The simulation was carried out under linear static condition (1 second time duration) using Abaqus. The 150KN force was applied at points a, b, c mentioned in Fig. 1. Different load application methods were studied, as the result end-loads make maximum stress concentration. For the initial time, the same blade thickness was maintained throughout the span to study the material characteristics. We assumed the thickness to be 40 mm. The result of numerical analysis provides the Tsai-Wu value to identify the failure occurrence in the blade structure. This failure appears, if the blade stress is more than the ultimate strength of the composite material towards the corresponding ply direction. This

Figure 5: Failure of blade with skin and spar made on glass fiber composite material

The cross-ply oriented carbon composite material provides less deflection but the stress concentration is high on 90° plies. The angle ply deflections are too high. The multi-ply arrangement provides damage resistance as well as less deflection. 45° ply provides less failure value, so it is placed close to outer layer in blade skin composite material. 90° plies are arranged closed to the mid layers, so the combination of 0°/90°/+45°/45° provides an acceptable stress and deflection.

As seen, the skin of the blade is aligned in multi-ply orientation. More 0° plies were added to improve the rigidity. The first and last plies of the skin is maintained 45° to act against shear stress concentration by wind. Note that the failure occurs only at the root sections.

Further in this study, failure criterion is explained for the following material combinations

- Blade with carbon woven fabrics skin and spar made of unidirectional carbon (type -1),
- Glass woven fabrics skin and spar made of unidirectional glass fiber composite (type -2),
- Glass woven fabrics skin and spar made of carbon unidirectional (type -3).

These configurations would be helpful to compare the material combination in different rotor components. The spar material represents the skin of the sandwich material used for spar web and spar flange. Spar sections are the basic load carrying components of the blade. Blade mass is based on spar material, because spar provide high stiffness and mass for complete blade structure.

After studying the material properties through orientations, the thickness of the blade should be optimized in order to reduce the weight and the gravitational force of the blade. Different thickness was used in the spar and the skin from root to tip section. Figure 3 shows how the blade model looks after its segregation. Each section allows giving the different thickness and material definition. The failure value of the blade after the thickness and material enhancement is shown in the Figures 4 and 5. Type-1, type-2 and type-3 configurations show approximatively the same value of failure (see table 3), but the location of failure origin is different between carbon skin blade and glass skin blade (see Figures 4,5). This is due because of the failure value at the root section is eliminated by the thickness optimization for type-1 blade. In this configuration, Tsai-Wu value at root section is much lower than 1. The failure concentration takes place at the leading and trailing edge's tip. In view of the fact that the shear property is perturbed by torsion load, but the type-2 and type-3 configurations show high stress distribution over the span and root (see Fig. 5). Significantly, this result report that only the material shear properties reinforcement allow type – 1 configuration to reduce the failure criterion value. The thickness optimization is carried out for type-2 configuration to avoid damage.

Table 3: Failure value identified by simulation after section blade segmentation

Type	Tsai-Wu criterion	Deflection	weight
Type -1	0.88	13.52 m	25671 Kg
Type -2	0.89	32.98 m	29455 Kg
Type -3	0.95	28.4 m	34894 Kg

The type-3 configuration provides good stiffness that reduces vertical displacement of the blade. The weight is lower than the type-2 configuration which is familiarly used nowadays. As per the cost basis study, type-3 configuration cost less than type-1. Furthermore, this part of numerical study shows the benefit of using different types of configuration based upon cost, mass and rigidity [23]. However, Type-3 configuration should be studied furthermore by considering issues of assembling two materials which have different aging parameters.

3.2 Composite attachments

The composite blades are assembled generally by adhesive materials with high shear modulus and tensile rigidity to avoid the separation of the blades even at the critical wind loading. The blade skin is made up of two main parts like top and bottom surfaces and they are glued by high performance adhesive material. In this simulation, we considered the adhesive as isotropic material [8], because the properties are the same in all directions. Equations (4), (5) show that shear and peeling stress act on the adhesive material under traction load. In our study, we use only the trailing and leading edge assembly methods. As the blade is bonded at the edges, the torsion load causes stress concentration along the trailing edge.

$$\sigma_z = \frac{E_s \epsilon_z}{(1 - \mu_p^2)} \cdot \epsilon_z \quad \text{-----} \quad (4)$$

$$\tau_x = \frac{E_s \gamma_x}{2(1 + \mu_p)} \quad \text{-----} \quad (5)$$

The failure value shows that damage is initiated in the adhesive zone. This value goes beyond the Tsai-Wu failure limit which is 1, Figure 7(a). From this result, we can notice that the adhesive bonding alone to fix the blade assembly parts would not be resistant enough. All 3 types of configuration provide same failure values, because of adhesive bonding damage initiation. Reinforcement in the adhesive region is needed to withstand damage in adhesive assembly area.

Figure 6: Bonding zones in a wind turbine blade

3.3 Advanced assembly method

As seen in previous results, adhesive bonding alone is not sufficient to withstand high load values. Also it shows that bonding is the weakest area where damage is initiated. So the advanced composite assembly called stitching is studied at a macroscopic level in this paper. Peel and shear stress values from equation 8, 9 can be added in equation 6, 7 which could give total shear and peel resistance value of the structure with stitching [10]. Also James et al. [6] have done research on the composite stitching and propose that composite stitching increases 38% of shear and tensile properties in bonding areas.

$$\tau^*(\gamma) = \tau(\gamma) + \tau_s(\gamma) \quad \text{----- (6)}$$

$$\sigma^*(\epsilon) = \sigma(\epsilon) + \sigma_s(\epsilon) \quad \text{----- (7)}$$

$$\sigma_s = F(1 - \frac{\gamma^2}{2}) \quad \text{----- (8)}$$

$$\tau_s = F\gamma \quad \text{----- (9)}$$

Figure 7 : (a) Failure in wind turbine blade trailing edge before including in the simulation stitching properties in adhesive material zones. (b) Failure in wind turbine blade trailing edge after including in the simulation stitching properties in the adhesive material zones.

Accordingly, numerical simulation properties are modified, and the result from this final model shows the failure value for 3 configurations. Type-1 provides less failure criterion value (26.6%) compared to fixing by adhesive bonding only Type-2 stays close to 1 even after stitching parameters are included. Type-3 configurations provide values in between other 2 configurations (see Fig.8). Type-1 configuration provides less failure factor, because the weak shear bonding property in the carbon skin is improved by composite stitching. Here, shear properties of carbon and stitches are performing together to reinforce the zone. Therefore, the damage occurrence is reduced. This combined effect of damage resistance is less for glass fiber skin that makes the failure value close to 1 for type-2 configuration (13% more than typ-1). Type-3 configuration undergoes this shared-resistance phenomenon by the presence of carbon composite material in the bonding area. Hence, the failure value is lower than type-2, but the assembly of two different materials may cause damage by environmental impacts [16, 20]. This study proves that composite stitching is really advised for the wind turbine blade assembly.

Figure 8: Failure criterion of blade before and after stitching (vertical axis values are Tsai-Wu failure criterion)

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study provides an overview of the behaviour of composite material blades under bending and torsion coupling load conditions. The woven fabrics composites are suitable for wind turbine blade skins. The blade section thickness should be optimized according to stress concentration zones. Root section and trailing edge sections are identified as high stress concentration areas. Multi-ply type lay-up orientation is preferable for wind turbine blade to minimise the failure and deflection. Torsion affects the trailing edges where shear resistance is less. Adhesive material located in these edges is not able to resist shear loads caused by blade torsion. Hence, bonding needs additional reinforcements, which could be brought by stitching. Composite stitching provides additional shear and peeling stress for the adhesive material. Composite stitching can hold the blade bonding areas even up to maximum crack extension. This reduces the failure occurrences at trailing and leading edges. The deformation of adhesive material is studied in different type of materials in different components. Maximum 26% of blade edge failure is reduced by including stitching property in the large scale numerical study. Therefore, stitching in the high stressed bonding zone is advised for large scale wind-turbine blades. This study can provide some support to wind turbine blade designers at the step level of manufacturing process. Further research on this project would improve the numerical simulations close to the real manufacturing process.

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